

Online Appendix - The US-China Trade War Creates Jobs (Elsewhere)*

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Online Appendix A: Overview of the Trade War

This Appendix summarizes key events of the US–China trade war during Trump’s first term. For details, see Bown and Kolb (2021).

The initial tension began in 2017, but the first tariff hikes took effect on March 23, 2018, when the US imposed a 25-percentage-point increase on steel tariffs and a 10-percentage-point increase on aluminum tariffs for most trading partners. China responded in early April with retaliatory tariffs on selected US goods (Bown, 2021).

The conflict escalated thereafter. On April 3, the US announced a 25-percentage-point tariff increase on over 1,000 Chinese products—worth \$50 billion. The next day, China released a reciprocal list of US products, also valued at \$50 billion and subject

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to the same tariff hike. On July 6, both countries imposed tariffs on \$34 billion of their respective lists, with the remaining \$16 billion taking effect on August 23.

In September 2018, the US announced a new round of tariff increases—ranging from 5 to 10 percentage points—on \$200 billion worth of 2017 imports from China. Shortly after, China issued a retaliatory list covering \$60 billion in US goods.

In 2019, the US carried out three additional rounds of tariff increases on Chinese products, each met with retaliatory measures from China. In May, the US raised tariffs by 15 percentage points on the \$200 billion list announced in September 2018. China responded by increasing tariffs on its \$60 billion list of US goods from the same period. In August, the US announced a new round targeting \$300 billion in Chinese imports, prompting Chinese tariffs on \$75 billion in US exports. The final tariff hike of 2019 came in December, with the US targeting phones, laptops, and video game consoles, while China imposed higher tariffs on cars and car parts. By January 2020, average US tariffs on Chinese goods were six times higher than in 2017.

In January 2020, China and the US signed the Phase One deal, which included provisions on purchase commitments, financial market access, and intellectual property protection. As part of the agreement, China committed to buy an additional \$200 billion worth of US exports, but tariffs remained at similarly high levels through 2024.

Online Appendix B: Additional Tables

This appendix presents three additional tables. Table B1 reports the correlation between Brazil's exports at the 6-digit HS product level and both China's imports from the United States and US imports from China. As shown, Brazil's exports are correlated with China's imports from the United States (0.5357), but exhibit almost no correlation with US imports from China (0.0126).

Table B2 presents descriptive statistics for the period 2012 to 2021 for our main outcome variables, based on the RAIS dataset at the microregion level. Panel A reports total formal employment, along with its mean and standard deviation, while Panel B displays the total formal wage bill, also with its mean and standard deviation. As we can see the mean formal employment was slightly negative from 2012 to 2021.

Table B1: Correlation Between Brazil's Exports, US Imports from China, and China's Imports from the US

Correlation	Brazil's Exports	China Imports from the US	US Imports from China
Brazil's Exports	1		
China Imports from the US	0.5357	1	
US Imports from China	0.0126	0.0261	1

Notes: Correlation between the 2016 value exported by Brazil, the value imported by China from the US, and the value imported by the US from China. Analysis conducted at 6-digit HS product code level.

Table B2: Descriptive Statistics

	t = 2012	t = 2013	t = 2014	t = 2015	t = 2016	t = 2017	t = 2018	t = 2019	t = 2020	t = 2021
Panel A. Employment										
Total (Millions)	37.56	38.59	38.25	36.77	35.28	35.19	35.67	34.40	33.48	37.04
Mean	67,309.26	69,162.29	68,543.05	65,893.83	63,216.23	63,066.01	63,918.16	61,642.69	59,990.33	66,371.19
Stf.Dev	271,541.15	274,673.22	271,564.41	258,904.64	247,000.95	244,026.82	246,573.27	235,901.67	225,616.23	248,665.97
Panel B. Wage Bill (R\$ Millions)										
Total (Millions)	86,447.61	91,508.83	98,902.18	92,980.29	89,960.96	90,534.30	90,606.82	85,780.40	82,082.02	88,209.40
Mean	154.92	163.99	177.24	166.63	161.22	162.25	162.38	153.73	147.10	158.08
Stf.Dev	807.70	840.34	901.06	847.51	808.45	804.92	806.04	770.47	728.85	790.30
Observations	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558

Notes: This table displays descriptive statistics across microregions for each outcome used in the paper by year. Each Panel displays the total value, mean, and standard deviation of the outcome. In Panel A, we show the statistics for the number of employment; Panel B displays the descriptive for the wage bill. Salaries are adjusted to 2016 values.

Table B3 presents regression results that include non-tradable industries in the calculation of employment share sums. As observed, the results are comparable to, or even stronger than, those reported in Table 1 of the paper.

Table B3: Regional Trade War Tariff Changes and Labor Outcomes - Including Non-Tradable Industries to Calculate Shares

Dep.Var: $\Delta_{16} \text{Log}(Y_t)$	After Trade War					Before Trade War			
	(1) t = 2021	(2) t = 2020	(3) t = 2019	(4) t = 2018	(5) t = 2017	(6) t = 2015	(7) t = 2014	(8) t = 2013	(9) t = 2012
Panel A. Formal Employment RTW_r^{CH}	0.029** (0.008)	0.031** (0.008)	0.024** (0.008)	0.012 (0.008)	0.009 (0.006)	0.018 (0.010)	0.013 (0.012)	0.011 (0.013)	0.006 (0.012)
Panel B. Formal Wages RTW_r^{CH}	0.031** (0.010)	0.033** (0.010)	0.034** (0.010)	0.017 (0.009)	0.015 (0.008)	0.018 (0.012)	0.013 (0.013)	0.006 (0.013)	0.003 (0.013)
Obs.	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558

Notes: Coefficients obtained from OLS regressions of the changes in the log of economic outcomes on an alternative version of Chinese regional trade war tariff changes. This alternative RTW_r^{CH} is calculated by including nontradable sectors when determining regions' industry employment shares. Each Panel displays the estimates using a different economic outcome. Economic outcomes used are: (Panel A) The number of formal workers, and (Panel B) the region's Wage bill. Columns (1) to (4) display the estimates for the years 2021 to 2018 (after trade war), column (5) displays the results for 2017, and columns (6) to (9) show the estimates for the years 2015 to 2012 (before trade war). All regressions include state-fixed effects, controls for the sum of shares and a set of baseline regional-level control variables: share of female workers, share of workers with a high school degree, share of workers under 30 years old, the microregion's GDP, and the share of workers employed in the agricultural sector. Standard errors in parentheses clustered at the mesoregion level (137 clusters). Significance at the *5%, ** 1% levels.

Finally, Table B4 displays the estimates for β_t^{CH} from equation (5) when using mesoregion-year fixed effects instead of state-year fixed effects. The results are very similar to those in Table 1, indicating that our conclusions are not driven by the level at which fixed effects are defined.

Table B4: Regional Trade War Tariff Changes and Labor Outcomes - Using Mesoregion Fixed Effects

Dep.Var: $\Delta_{16} \text{Log}(Y_t)$	After Trade War					Before Trade War			
	(1) t = 2021	(2) t = 2020	(3) t = 2019	(4) t = 2018	(5) t = 2017	(6) t = 2015	(7) t = 2014	(8) t = 2013	(9) t = 2012
Panel A. Formal Employment									
RTR_r^{CH}	0.021* (0.010)	0.020 (0.010)	0.022* (0.009)	0.020 (0.017)	0.010 (0.006)	0.006 (0.012)	0.002 (0.012)	0.002 (0.013)	0.011 (0.023)
Panel B. Formal Wages									
RTR_r^{CH}	0.028* (0.012)	0.024 (0.013)	0.030** (0.011)	0.021 (0.016)	0.016 (0.010)	0.007 (0.014)	-0.006 (0.016)	-0.005 (0.015)	0.017 (0.027)
Obs.	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558

Notes: Coefficients obtained from OLS regressions of the changes in the log of economic outcomes on 2019 Chinese regional trade war tariff changes. Each Panel displays the estimates using a different economic outcome. Economic outcomes used are: (Panel A) The number of formal workers, and (Panel B) the region's Wage bill. Columns (1) to (4) display the estimates for the years 2021 to 2018 (after trade war), column (5) displays the results for 2017, and columns (6) to (9) show the estimates for the years 2015 to 2012 (before trade war). All regressions include mesoregion-year fixed effects, controls for the sum of shares and a set of baseline regional-level control variables: share of female workers, share of workers with a high school degree, share of workers under 30 years old, the microregion's GDP, and the share of workers employed in the agricultural sector. Standard errors in parentheses clustered at the mesoregion level (137 clusters). Significance at the *5%, ** 1% levels.

Online Appendix C: Additional Figures

This appendix reports four additional figures. Figure C1 presents the evolution of Brazilian exports by destination. As illustrated, beginning in 2016, Brazilian exports to China increased substantially, while exports to other major destinations remained relatively constant.

Figure C1: Brazilian Exports by Destination

Notes: This figure shows the value of Brazil's exports (in billions of current US dollars) to its main trading partners over time. Each line corresponds to the value exported to a specific partner: China (red diamond), the US (blue circle), Japan (yellow triangle), Mercosur (green square), and the European Union (orange X). The vertical line indicates the year preceding the onset of the tariff escalation.

Figure C2 presents the estimates of θ_k from equation (2), including not-yet-treated products as part of the control group. Panel A reports the estimated effects on the value of Brazilian exports to China (Panel A.1) and to the US (Panel A.2), while Panel B displays the effects on the quantity exported to China (Panel B.1) and to the US (Panel B.2).

Figure C2: Impact of Trade War Tariffs on Brazilian Exports: Including Not-Yet-Treated Products in the Control Group

Notes: Each dot represents the estimated coefficient θ_k from Equation (2), where not-yet-treated products are included in the control group. In Panel A, the dependent variable is the logarithm of one plus the value exported (in dollars of 2016, deflated using the US CPI) to China (Panel A.1) or the US (Panel A.2). In Panel B, the dependent variable is the logarithm of one plus the quantity exported (in kilograms) to China (Panel B.1) or the US (Panel B.2). Bars represent 95% confidence intervals. Standard errors are clustered at the HS 4-digit level.

Figure C3 presents the estimates from equation (2), but restricting the sample to products within 4-digit HS code groups for which at least one product received a discriminatory tariff during the sample period. By doing this, we exclude nine 4-digit HS product groups. The results for Chinese exports remain very similar to the main specification. For US exports, the coefficients are mostly not statistically significant, but exhibit

a negative pattern, suggesting that exports to the US may have experienced a slight reduction.

Figure C3: Impact of Trade War Tariffs on Brazilian Exports: Excluding Untargeted 4-Digit HS Groups

Notes: Each dot represents the estimated coefficient θ_k from Equation (2), where untargeted 4-digit HS groups were excluded from the analysis. In Panel A, the dependent variable is the logarithm of one plus the value exported (in dollars of 2016, deflated using the US CPI) to China (Panel A.1) or the US (Panel A.2). In Panel B, the dependent variable is the logarithm of one plus the quantity exported (in kilograms) to China (Panel B.1) or the US (Panel B.2). Bars represent 95% confidence intervals. Standard errors are clustered at the HS 4-digit level.

Figure C4 presents the estimated impacts of the trade war tariffs on Brazilian exports to the rest of the world (excluding China and the United States), based on the staggered Callaway and Sant’Anna difference-in-differences specification. The results show positive effects on both the value and quantity exported, suggesting that the increase in

exports to China did not come at the expense of trade with other destinations.

Figure C4: Impact of Trade War Tariffs on Brazilian Exports to the Rest of the World

Notes: Each dot represents the estimated coefficient θ_k from Equation (2). In Panel A, the dependent variable is the logarithm of one plus the value exported (in dollars of 2016, deflated using the US CPI) to the rest of the world (ROW) –all countries except China and the US). In Panel B, the dependent variable is the logarithm of one plus the quantity exported (in kilograms) to the ROW. Bars represent 95% confidence intervals. Standard errors are clustered at the HS 4-digit level.

Figures C5 and C6 display the estimates of the impact of Brazilian regions' exposure to the US–China trade war tariffs on the number of formal jobs and regional wage bills, respectively. Those are the coefficients estimated in the specification with the US tariffs reported Panels A.2 and B.2 in Table 1. The results indicate that regions more exposed to Chinese retaliatory tariffs against the US experienced a relative increase in formal employment and wage bills. However, there is no evidence of an effect for regions more exposed to US tariffs on China.

Figure C5: Employment Impact of Exposure to Trade War Tariffs

Notes: Each dot represents the estimated coefficients obtained from OLS regressions of the changes in the log of the number of formal workers on 2019 Chinese and American regional trade war tariff changes. Blue circles represents the impacts of the American discriminatory tariffs, while red triangles represents the impact from the Chinese retaliatory tariffs. Bars show 95 percent confidence intervals. Standard errors are adjusted for 137 mesoregion clusters. All regressions include state-fixed effects and a set of baseline regional-level control variables: share of female workers, share of workers with a high school degree, share of workers under 30 years old, the microregion's GDP, and the share of workers employed in the agricultural sector.

Figure C6: Wage Impact of Exposure to Trade War Tariffs

Notes: Each dot represents the estimated coefficients obtained from OLS regressions of the changes in the log of region's Wage bill on 2019 Chinese and American regional trade war tariff changes. Blue circles represents the impacts of the American discriminatory tariffs, while red triangles represents the impact from the Chinese retaliatory tariffs. Bars show 95 percent confidence intervals. Standard errors are adjusted for 137 mesoregion clusters. All regressions include state-fixed effects and a set of baseline regional-level control variables: share of female workers, share of workers with a high school degree, share of workers under 30 years old, the microregion's GDP, and the share of workers employed in the agricultural sector.

Online Appendix D: RAIS Data

The Annual Relation of Social Information (RAIS) is an administrative data set reported by the Brazilian Ministry of Labor that provides high-quality data of Brazilian formal labor market. RAIS was instituted by the decree n° 76.900 on December 23 of 1975 to (i) Provide information regarding the formal labor market in Brazil, (ii) monitor the entry of foreign workers in the Brazilian labor market. (iii) provides statistical information for government decisions (iv) generate data for different governmental benefit programs as FGTS, unemployment insurances, PIS, PASEP, and “abono salarial.”

Since report the information on every formal employee is a costly task for companies, the federal government created a mechanism to guarantee that the information reported are complete and accurate. First, companies that delay sending data or send false or incomplete information face fines until they send the complete information. Second, some governmental benefits paid to workers are conditional on having their job information correctly declared in RAIS. Hence, workers have an incentive to require the employer to send the correct information. Therefore, both workers and employers have an incentive to report accurate and complete information to the Ministry of labor, ensuring the quality of the data.

We collect the following information of RAIS:

1. The number of formal employees in each industry for the years between 2012 and 2021: To construct this variable, we considered only individuals between 15 and 64 years old, employed on the last day of December, and with a positive earning in that month. In cases in which the same worker appeared twice in the sample, we keep only the highest paying job in December.
2. We also collect data on formal employees' wages in December of each year. Based on individual wages, we calculate the total wage bill for each microregion during this month. December wages are used because data for this period is considered the most reliable.

Online Appendix E: Correspondence Between HS and CNAE Codes

The tariff and trade data used in the analysis are reported at the 6-digit product-level HS code, whereas the employment data from RAIS are reported at the CNAE 2.0 level, an economic activity classification. To map the product-level data to CNAE 2.0, we utilized the following correspondences:

1. A correspondence between 6-digit HS codes (revision 2012) and 5-digit CPC codes (revision 2.1), obtained from the WITS website.¹
2. A correspondence between 5-digit CPC codes (revision 2.1) and ISIC economic activity codes (version 4.0), also sourced from the WITS website.
3. A correspondence from ISIC 4.0 to CNAE 2.0 codes (the economic activity classification reported in RAIS data), obtained from the CONCLA website.²

During this process, 113 products (2.17% of all products at the 6-digit HS level) were excluded because they do not have a correspondent CNAE industry code.

After establishing the correspondence between 6-digit HS codes and CNAE 2.0 codes, we aggregated industry codes that were composed of the same set of products. This process resulted in 177 tradable industries. Additionally, we combined six industries into three broader categories due to high similarity (See Table E1). The final correspondence includes 174 activity codes.

For robustness, we replicated our analysis without aggregating these 11 industries. The findings remained virtually unchanged, confirming that the aggregation process does not affect the overall results or the conclusions of our analysis.

¹https://wits.worldbank.org/product_concordance.html

²<https://concla.ibge.gov.br/classificacoes/correspondencias/atividades-economicas.html>

Table E1: Industries Aggregated due to similarity

New Group	CNAE 2.0 Codes	Group with the same products	Number of products	Observation
Group 1	14134	1	215	1) CNAE codes 14134, 14126, and 14118 consist of exactly the same set of products. 2) All 215 products in these three industries are also included in industry 14142.
	14126		215	
	14118		215	
	14142	2	218	
Group 2	28259	1	65	1) CNAE codes 28259, 28232, and 28241 consist of exactly the same set of products. 2) All 65 products in these three industries are also included in industry 28291.
	28232		65	
	28241		65	
	28291	2	86	
Group 3	20223	1	480	1) CNAE codes 20223,20118, 20215, 19322, 20142, 20193, 19314 consist of exactly the same set of products. 2) All 480 products in these seven industries are also included in industry 20291.
	20118		480	
	20215		480	
	19322		480	
	20142		480	
	20193		480	
	19314		480	
	20291	2	482	

Online Appendix F: Controls for MFN Tariff Changes

This appendix presents complementary analyses examining the potential confounding effects of changes in China’s MFN tariffs during the trade war period. We first document the absence of a significant correlation between MFN and trade war tariffs at the product level. We then describe the construction of the MFN tariff change controls used in the robustness exercises.

During the Trade War, China also changed their MFN import tariffs to the rest of the world. If those MFN tariff changes are correlated with the trade war tariffs imposed on the American imports, then the interpretation of the estimates presented Panel A.1 and B.1 of Table 1 as the causal impact of the trade war would be compromised. As a first check, Table F1 presents the correlation between the MFN tariff changes from 2016 to 2019 and the discriminatory tariffs imposed during the trade war until 2019 at the product level. The coefficients indicate that these tariffs are not correlated. Therefore, variations in MFN tariffs are not expected to contaminate the results presented in the previous section.

Table F1: Correlation Between Trade War Tariffs and MFN Tariff Changes

Correlation	$\tau_{CH,2019,p}^{TW}$	$\tau_{US,2019,p}^{TW}$	$\tau_{CH,2019,p}^{MFN}$	$\tau_{US,2019,p}^{MFN}$
$\tau_{CH,2019,p}^{TW}$	1			
$\tau_{US,2019,p}^{TW}$	0.0538	1		
$\tau_{CH,2019,p}^{MFN}$	-0.1306	0.1647	1	
$\tau_{US,2019,p}^{MFN}$	-0.0259	-0.0497	0.0290	1

Notes: Correlation between trade war tariffs and MFN tariff changes from 2016 to 2019. Analysis conducted at 6-digit HS product code level.

To conduct a more formal test and guarantee that the MFN tariff reductions are not influencing our findings, we estimate regression (5) controlling for a possible confounding effect coming from MFN tariff changes. The MFN tariff change controls are constructed similarly to the regional trade war tariff changes, but using the difference in MFN tariffs instead of trade war-induced tariff increase. Also, observe that the defini-

tion of the trade flow affected differs when considering the MFN tariff changes. Hence, the MFN regional tariff change ($RTC_{MFN,r}^{C1}$) controls for country $C1$ is calculated as:

$$RTC_{MFN,r}^{C1} = \sum^I \lambda_{ri} \frac{M_{i,2016}^{C1 \leftarrow W}}{M_{i,2016}^W} [\ln(1 + \tau_{C1,i,2019}^{MFN}) - \ln(1 + \tau_{C1,i,2016}^{MFN})],$$

where $M_{i,2016}^{C1 \leftarrow W}$ is the total value imported by country $C1$ of products in industry i in 2016, $\tau_{C1,i,t}^{MFN}$ is the MFN tariff imposed by country $C1$ on in industry i 's products in year t .

Online Appendix G: Robustness Tests

This section demonstrates that our findings are robust to alternative model specifications and different measures of regional exposure to trade war tariff changes. Tables G1 and G2 present the robustness tests for the impacts of the trade war on employment and regions' wage bills, respectively. For reference, Panel A in each table replicates the estimates from the main specification. The subsequent panels provide the estimates for the alternative approaches, which are explained in detail in the remainder of this section.

Table G1: Robustness: Regional Trade War Tariff Changes and Formal Employment

Dep.Var: $\Delta_{16} \text{Log}(\text{Employment}_t)$	After Trade War					Before Trade War			
	(1) t = 2021	(2) t = 2020	(3) t = 2019	(4) t = 2018	(5) t = 2017	(6) t = 2015	(7) t = 2014	(8) t = 2013	(9) t = 2012
Panel A. Main Specification									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.021* (0.009)	0.023** (0.008)	0.020* (0.008)	0.018 (0.012)	0.008 (0.005)	0.012 (0.009)	0.004 (0.009)	-0.000 (0.010)	0.004 (0.016)
Panel B. Alternative RTW_r^{CH} - Including 2016 MFN									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.021* (0.009)	0.023** (0.008)	0.020* (0.008)	0.018 (0.012)	0.009 (0.006)	0.012 (0.009)	0.004 (0.009)	-0.000 (0.010)	0.004 (0.016)
Panel C. Alternative RTW_r^{CH} - GMI_{alt-1}									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.018* (0.008)	0.019** (0.007)	0.018** (0.006)	0.018 (0.013)	0.007 (0.004)	0.009 (0.008)	0.003 (0.009)	-0.000 (0.010)	0.005 (0.018)
Panel D. Alternative RTW_r^{CH} - GMI_{alt-2}									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.022** (0.008)	0.024** (0.008)	0.020* (0.008)	0.017 (0.011)	0.010 (0.006)	0.009 (0.009)	0.000 (0.009)	-0.007 (0.009)	-0.000 (0.013)
Panel E. Trade War Tariffs until 2018									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.020* (0.008)	0.023** (0.007)	0.019** (0.007)	0.011 (0.008)	0.007 (0.005)	0.013 (0.009)	0.006 (0.009)	0.004 (0.010)	0.000 (0.012)
Obs.	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558

Notes: Coefficients obtained from OLS regressions of the changes in the log of the number of formal employment on Chinese regional trade war tariff changes. Panel A displays the estimates from the main specification. Panel B show the estimates for the main specification but an alternative version of the RTW_r^{CH} in which we consider the log difference in trade war tariffs plus MFN tariffs in 2016. Panels C and D also test alternative exposure measures, using the squared and square root of the affected trade flows to construct the GMI, respectively. Panel E estimates the main specification but the RTW_r^{CH} is constructed using the trade war tariffs implemented until 2018. Columns (1) to (4) display the estimates for the years 2021 to 2018 (after trade war), column (5) displays the results for 2017, and columns (6) to (9) show the estimates for the years 2015 to 2012 (before trade war). All regressions include state-fixed effects and a set of baseline regional-level control variables: share of female workers, share of workers with a high school degree, share of workers under 30 years old, the microregion's GDP, and the share of workers employed in the agricultural sector. Standard errors in parentheses clustered at the mesoregion level (137 clusters). Significance at the *5%, ** 1% levels.

G.1 Alternative Measure for Regional Trade War Tariff Changes

One might question whether the effect of tariff hikes could be less pronounced for products that were already subject to higher MFN tariffs prior to the conflict, compared to those previously untariffed. To address this, Panel B of Tables G1 and G2 presents the estimates using an alternative version of RTW_r^{CH} that accounts for the difference in tar-

iffs relative to their initial levels. This alternative version of the exposure variable is constructed as follows:

$$RTW_r^{CH} = \sum^I \lambda_{r,t} \frac{\overbrace{M_{i,2016}^{CH \leftarrow US}}^{GMI_{i,t}^{CH}}}{M_{i,2016}^W} \underbrace{\left[\ln(1 + \tau_{CH,2019,i}^{TW} + \tau_{CH,2016,i}^{MFN}) - \ln(1 + \tau_{C1,2016,i}^{MFN}) \right]}_{\Delta \tau_{i,t}^{C1 \leftarrow C2}}.$$

where, $\tau_{C1,2016,i}^{MFN}$ is the 2016 MFN tariff imposed by China on products from industry i .

The coefficients in Panel B are nearly identical to those in the main specification, suggesting that the results from this alternative approach similarly capture the impacts of the trade war on economic outcomes. This consistency indicates that the initial MFN tariff levels of products do not significantly influence the estimated effects.

Table G2: Robustness: Regional Trade War Tariff Changes and Formal Wages

Dep. Var: $\Delta_{16} \text{Log}(\text{Earnings}_i)$	After Trade War					Before Trade War			
	(1) t = 2021	(2) t = 2020	(3) t = 2019	(4) t = 2018	(5) t = 2017	(6) t = 2015	(7) t = 2014	(8) t = 2013	(9) t = 2012
Panel A. Main Specification									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.023* (0.011)	0.025* (0.011)	0.028** (0.010)	0.020 (0.012)	0.013 (0.008)	0.014 (0.011)	0.001 (0.011)	-0.006 (0.011)	0.008 (0.018)
Panel B. Alternative RTW_r^{CH} - Including 2016 MFN									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.024* (0.011)	0.025* (0.011)	0.028** (0.011)	0.020 (0.013)	0.013 (0.009)	0.014 (0.011)	0.001 (0.012)	-0.005 (0.011)	0.009 (0.018)
Panel C. Alternative RTW_r^{CH} - GMI_{alt-1}									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.016 (0.009)	0.016 (0.009)	0.022* (0.009)	0.016 (0.012)	0.010 (0.006)	0.011 (0.010)	0.001 (0.010)	-0.003 (0.011)	0.013 (0.020)
Panel D. Alternative RTW_r^{CH} - GMI_{alt-2}									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.029** (0.011)	0.031** (0.011)	0.033** (0.012)	0.023 (0.012)	0.016 (0.010)	0.012 (0.012)	-0.005 (0.012)	-0.014 (0.010)	0.001 (0.016)
Panel E. Trade War Tariffs until 2018									
RTW_r^{CH}	0.022* (0.010)	0.026** (0.009)	0.026** (0.009)	0.015 (0.009)	0.012 (0.007)	0.014 (0.011)	0.003 (0.011)	-0.003 (0.011)	-0.002 (0.014)
Obs.	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558

Notes: Coefficients obtained from OLS regressions of the changes in the log of region's wage bill on Chinese regional trade war tariff changes. Panel A displays the estimates from the main specification. Panel B show the estimates for the main specification but an alternative version of the RTW_r^{CH} in which we consider the log difference in trade war tariffs plus MFN tariffs in 2016. Panels C and D also test alternative exposure measures, using the squared and square root of the affected trade flows to construct the GMI, respectively. Panel E also estimates the main specification but the RTW_r^{CH} is constructed using the trade war tariffs implemented until 2018. Columns (1) to (4) display the estimates for the years 2021 to 2018 (after trade war), column (5) displays the results for 2017, and columns (6) to (9) show the estimates for the years 2015 to 2012 (before trade war). All regressions include state-fixed effects and a set of baseline regional-level control variables: share of female workers, share of workers with a high school degree, share of workers under 30 years old, the microregion's GDP, and the share of workers employed in the agricultural sector. Standard errors in parentheses clustered at the mesoregion level (137 clusters). Significance at the *5%, ** 1% levels.

G.2 Alternative Measures for Global Market Impact

To assess the robustness of our results to different specifications of the exposure measure, we also construct the GMI using alternative transformations of the affected trade flow. Specifically, we consider two additional specifications: one using the squared value of the affected trade flow (GMI_{alt-1}^{C1}) and another using its square root (GMI_{alt-2}^{C1}). That is:

$$GMI_{alt-1}^{C1} = \left[\frac{M_{i,2016}^{C1 \leftarrow C2}}{M_{i,2016}^W} \right]^2 \log(1 + \tau_{C1,i,2019}^{TW}), \quad (1)$$

$$GMI_{alt-2}^{C1} = \sqrt{\frac{M_{i,2016}^{C1 \leftarrow C2}}{M_{i,2016}^W}} \log(1 + \tau_{C1,i,2019}^{TW}), \quad (2)$$

Panels C and D present the results when constructing RTW_r^{CH} using GMI_{alt-1}^{C1} and GMI_{alt-2}^{C1} , respectively. The results obtained with these alternative measures remain consistent with those from our main specification, suggesting that our findings are not sensitive to the functional form of the trade exposure variable.

G.3 Estimating the impacts using trade war tariffs until 2018

In the main specification, we estimate the impacts of the trade war for all years using regional exposure to the discriminatory tariffs imposed by China up to the end of 2019. However, one might question whether the results, particularly the impacts in 2018, would differ if we used only the trade war tariffs imposed by the end of 2018. To address this concern, we re-estimate the main specification by constructing RTW_r^{CH} based solely on the Chinese discriminatory tariffs in place by the end of 2018.

The results of this exercise are presented in Panel E of Tables G1 and G2. The estimates in columns (1) to (4) are similar to those from the main specification, although slightly smaller, as expected, since the exposure variable does not fully capture the shock faced by the most exposed regions. Overall, the estimated coefficients in this specification closely align with those from the main specification, confirming the robustness of the results to this alternative specification.

Online Appendix H: Comparative Advantage and Product Differentiation

In Table B1 of Appendix B we show that Brazil’s exports are positively correlated with China’s imports from the United States (0.5357), but exhibit almost no correlation with US imports from China (0.0126).

This appendix presents a series of analyses designed to explore why Brazilian regional labor markets respond more strongly to Chinese tariffs than to US. tariffs. Once the product-level tariff shocks are aggregated into a regional exposure measure based on local industry composition, it might seem that the origin of the tariffs should not matter. However, this may not hold in practice if Brazil is not well positioned to capture the additional demand generated by certain tariff changes.

We see at least two mechanisms through which this can occur. First, Brazil may have a stronger comparative advantage in the products it typically exports to China than in the products it typically exports to the United States, making it better positioned to respond to changes in Chinese demand. Second, the degree of product differentiation may affect how easily Brazilian producers can adjust their output: more differentiated products typically involve greater rigidity in market structure and higher adaptation costs, which could limit Brazil’s ability to respond to trade diversion.

To investigate these mechanisms empirically, we conduct three complementary analyses.

In the first analysis, we compute the average of Balassa (1965)’s index of Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Brazilian exports in 2016, weighted by each product’s share in Brazil’s exports to China and to the United States, respectively. RCA values are calculated at the 6-digit HS (rev. 2012) level as:

$$RCA_p^{BR} = \frac{\frac{X_p^{BR}}{\sum_{p' \in P} X_{p'}^{BR}}}{\frac{X_p^W}{\sum_{p' \in P} X_{p'}^W}},$$

where X_p^{BR} and X_p^W denote Brazilian and world exports of product p , respectively. The weighted average RCA across products uses each product’s share in Brazil’s exports to

China or to the United States. Results, presented in the first row of Table H1, show that Brazil’s comparative advantage is substantially higher for products exported to China than for those exported to the United States, suggesting that Brazil is better positioned to respond to trade diversion in the Chinese market.

Table H1: Comparative Advantage and Product Differentiation

Indicator	China	US
Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA)	20.87	8.83
Rauch Conservative (US and CH)	0.55	0.95
Rauch Liberal (US and CH)	0.53	0.92
Rauch conservative (BR)	0.05	0.55
Rauch Liberal (BR)	0.05	0.47

Notes: The table reports measures of Brazil’s comparative advantage and product differentiation for exports to China and the United States. RCA shows the average Revealed Comparative Advantage of Brazilian exports in 2016, weighted by the share of each product in Brazil’s exports to the respective destination. Rauch Conservative (US and CH) and Rauch Liberal (US and CH) report the share of differentiated products among those affected by discriminatory tariffs, based on Rauch (1999) classifications at the 4-digit SITC rev.2 level. Rauch Conservative (BR) and Rauch Liberal (BR) report the share of differentiated products in Brazilian exports to China and the U.S., weighted by export values.

In the second analysis, we examine whether the products targeted by Chinese and US tariffs differ in terms of product differentiation. We rely on the classification from Rauch (1999) , which categorizes 4-digit SITC rev.2 products as “differentiated,” “reference priced,” or “traded on an organized exchange.”³ This dataset provides both a conservative and a liberal classification, and results are reported for both. Using UN Comtrade correspondence tables, SITC codes are matched to 6-digit HS (rev. 2012) codes and merged with the tariff datasets.⁴ Of the 5,204 HS6 products, 228 could not be matched and were excluded; robustness checks assigning all unmatched products as either differentiated or non-differentiated yield similar qualitative results.⁵

³Rauch (1999) classification can be downloaded in https://econweb.ucsd.edu/~jrauch/rauch_classification.html.

⁴The correspondence between SITC rev 2 and 2012 HS codes can be downloaded in <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/classifications/Econ>.

⁵When merging the Rauch (1999) classification with the SITC Rev. 2-to-HS 2012 correspondence, 489 SITC products from the Rauch classification lack a match in the HS nomenclature. Consequently, 228 HS products are missing a Rauch classification for differentiated products.

We then create indicator variables equal to 1 if a product was subject to a discriminatory Chinese tariff (applied to US goods) or a discriminatory US tariff (applied to Chinese goods). These data are merged with trade values—Chinese imports from the US and US imports from China in 2016—to compute the share of differentiated products affected by each set of tariffs. Specifically, we calculate the trade-weighted average of the “differentiated” indicator for products affected by Chinese tariffs (weighted by the share of each product in total Chinese imports from the US) and for products affected by US tariffs (weighted by the share of each product in total US imports from China). Results, shown in the second and third rows of Table H1, indicate that products affected by Chinese tariffs are generally less differentiated than those affected by US tariffs, suggesting that trade diversion from Chinese tariffs involves more homogeneous products, which can be more easily supplied by alternative exporters such as Brazil.

In the third analysis, we examine the degree of product differentiation in Brazilian exports to each destination. Using the Rauch (1999) classification, we calculate the share of differentiated products in Brazil’s exports to China and to the United States, weighting by each product’s importance in total exports to that market. Results, reported in the fourth and fifth rows of Table H1, show that Brazilian exports to the United States are more differentiated than those to China, indicating that Brazilian producers face lower adaptation costs when responding to increased demand from China.

Taken together, these analyses help explain why Brazilian regional labor markets respond primarily to Chinese tariffs.

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